

A NEW PROPAGATION PREDICTION TOOL FOR EARTH-SPACE GEOMETRIES FOR THE ADVANCED REFRACTIVE EFFECTS PREDICTION SYSTEM (AREPS)

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ABSTRACT

*AREPS is the U.S. Navy's designated software tool ** for radar performance simulation and analysis. For well over 20 years it has been used to provide accurate propagation predictions in realistic refractive environments for terrestrial radar systems from VHF (~100 MHz) to Q-band (~60 GHz). Recently, the range of applications for AREPS has been extended by the addition of a communications prediction capability at high frequencies (HF, ~2 MHz – 30 MHz) which includes both surface wave and ionospheric sky wave coverage for beyond line-of-sight propagation paths. In this paper we describe the latest addition to AREPS, which uses refractive height profile input along with a newly developed ray trace capability to provide signal strength estimates for earth-to-satellite communications. By including atmospheric refractivity the model becomes especially useful for determination of antenna pointing angles in strongly refracting environments and for low-elevation satellites for which ray paths through the atmosphere may be very long. The model includes an orbital location prediction capability which uses two-line element sets (TLE) which are widely available on the internet for non-classified systems and generally available for classified systems for designated users. The model provides a transparent homing procedure which determines the launch angle for the direct ray connecting transmitter to satellite and, in some situations, for the earth reflected mode. Possible ray blockage by terrain for low elevation satellites can be investigated by including DTED terrain elevation data in the analysis.*

INTRODUCTION

AREPS is a well known analysis and prediction tool for radar systems operating in the VHF to Q-band frequency regime. Recently, the applications of AREPS have been extended to HF surface wave radar through the addition of a surface wave calculation to the Advanced Propagation Model (APM), which is the core propagation engine within AREPS (Barrios, et.al., 2007).

Similarly, we have extended the applications of the

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AREPS software to include communication system design and analysis. Currently, the communication capabilities include HF sky wave coverage analysis, HF point-to-point analysis and a combined HF sky wave and ground wave prediction capability for short propagation paths. A three-dimensional ray trace capability has also been added to give the user a tool for more in-depth study and analysis of HF propagation conditions on a circuit than can be obtained from the other models.

In this paper we describe an earth to satellite propagation prediction tool which is the latest addition to the communication capabilities of AREPS. The new tool, which we have named the Earth-to-Satellite Propagation Model with Meteorology (ESPM2), employs a ray tracing capability in a user specified refractive environment to determine parameters such as carrier signal strength, carrier signal-to-noise ratio (or bit error rates for digital systems), antenna pointing angles and accumulated phase for direct and, in certain cases, earth-reflected rays connecting a transmitting station to a satellite. In the determination of carrier signal strength we include the effects of rain attenuation and gaseous absorption for all modes. For earth reflected modes we also include losses due to earth reflection and energy density spread due to the curved earth. More recently, a simple ionospheric electron density specification model has been implemented which allows the total electron content (TEC) to be estimated along the 'homed' rays. With this new capability the effects of the background ionosphere on digital signal characteristics such as signal delay and spread can also be determined. In the following section we present a short description of the ray tracing method used in ESPM2 and the assumptions made in extending the refractivity profile to satellite heights.

RAY TRACING IN ESPM2

The ray tracing capability developed for ESPM2 assumes that major refractive gradients exist in the height-range plane only and so ignores gradients normal to that plane. Consequently, rays launched in the azimuthal direction of the satellite, as viewed from a ground based transmitter, remain in the initial azimuthal plane.

In the homing procedure, test rays are launched at various angles from the height of the transmitting antenna. The initial launch angle for the direct ray is the angle determined by the straight line connecting the transmitter to the satellite. Subsequent launch angles are adjusted until the ray path intersects the satellite orbit at the instantaneous position of the satellite.

For the earth reflected mode, the homing procedure is two-dimensional since the range to the reflection point is not known initially. Thus not only is the launch angle varied in the homing process, but the point of reflection is also adjusted. The process continues until the point of reflection is determined at which equal reflection angles exist for the rays connecting the ground point to the transmitter and the ground point to the satellite (Sprague, 2008). Figure 3 shows the convergence process for the direct ray in the homing procedure.

We expect the ESPM2 model to be especially useful for determining rays connecting transmitter and satellite in realistic refractive environments at low elevation angles. For these low angle rays, the probability of mode cut-off due to ground terrain or man-made structures near the transmit antennas increases. In order to investigate this possibility for an arbitrary transmit location, we have

Once the azimuth from transmit antenna to the satellite is established, the DTED database is accessed to obtain the terrain profile along that azimuth from the transmit antenna. With the homed ray determined, the ray is re-traced, checking for terrain cut-off at every height step until the ray has cleared the top of the terrain profile. An example of this process is shown in Figure 3, which shows the cut-off of rays by the naturally occurring terrain. Current plans call for adding the capability for man-made structures to be added to the DTED data for this purpose.

Figure 4. (U) Illustration of mode cut-off due to intervening terrain. Refractive environment is the same as shown in Figure 2.

Implicit in the above discussion has been the assumption that the satellite location is known at all times. For communication to geostationary satellites, the location may be known well enough for some users needs. Generally, however, it is necessary to use an orbital prediction program to predict where the satellite is in its orbit at the time one wishes to communicate. This is especially true for orbiting satellites whose position may change very quickly with time.

For the ESPM2 program we have included the 'sdp4' and 'sgp4' orbital prediction programs developed for NORAD by Hoots and Roehrich (1988). The 'sdp4' program is used for long orbital period satellites and 'sgp4' short (< 255 minutes) period satellites. The applicable program in any situation is determined by the program and is transparent to the user.

Input to either program is contained in the two line element set (TLE), which is an ascii data file containing the ephemeris data necessary for calculating the satellite position. The TLE files are updated regularly for most satellites and may be obtained online for non-classified

Figure 3. (U) Illustrating the homing process for direct ray in ESPM2. The vertical axis is the difference between the range to the sub-satellite point and the range at which the ray intersects the orbital path.

included access to the National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency Level 1 Digital Terrain Elevation Data (DTED) .

systems. For access to controlled satellites the TLE is also usually available online via siprnet.

With the ray(s) which connect transmitter to satellite determined, the expected signal strength at the satellite can be calculated for each mode. We note that earth reflected modes are not included in the analysis unless the reflection point is determined to be sea-water. For an arbitrary terrain type the assumption of specular reflection is virtually never satisfied and the existence of a single reflected mode, even if its location could be determined, is problematic at best. For sea-water reflections, the specular reflection may be strong enough to contribute coherently to the total field in a deterministic way, as described in the next section.

SIGNAL STRENGTH CALCULATIONS

The result of the ray trace homing procedure is the launch and reception angles for the ray(s) which connect the transmit antenna to the satellite in the specified realistic refractive environment. We also determine the ray path length for each mode $x_{d(r)}$, including the reflected mode if it is calculated. In general, the signal strength at the satellite can be written

$$\vec{E}_t = \vec{E}_d \exp(ik\phi_d) + \vec{E}_r \exp(ik\phi_r) \quad (3)$$

where $|E_t|$ is the total field amplitude, $|E_d|$ is the direct field amplitude, $|E_r|$ is the earth reflected field amplitude, k is the free space wave number, and

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_d &= p_d + p_0, \\ \phi_r &= p_r + \arg(R)/k. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Here, p_0 is the initial phase of the direct ray relative to the reflected ray and $p_{d(r)}$ is the phase path length given by

$$p_d = \int_t^s n ds_d, p_r = \int_t^g n ds_r + \int_g^s n ds_r \quad (5)$$

where t is the transmitter location, s is the satellite location, and g is the ground reflection point. In this equation, $ds_{d(r)}$ is a ray element along the direct (reflected) ray path, which is determined by the ray trace program, and n is the index of refraction.

The reflected field amplitude in (3) is composed of several terms to account for reflections from a non-perfectly conducting, curved-earth surface. Thus, it is assumed that the reflected field amplitude can be written as

$$\vec{E}_r = \vec{E}_0 |R| D \quad (6)$$

where $|E_0|$ is the amplitude of a wave reflected from a smooth, flat, perfectly conducting tangent plane at the reflection point after traversing a total distance, x_r , to the satellite, and

$$|R| \exp(\arg(R)) \quad (7)$$

is the complex Fresnel reflection coefficient that accounts for the effects of a finitely conducting earth and is given by Kerr (1951) as

$$R = \frac{\sin(\theta_g) - \Delta}{\sin(\theta_g) + \Delta}$$

where θ_g is the grazing angle of the ray at the earth's surface and Δ is the complex normalized surface impedance given for a horizontally polarized wave by $(\eta \cos^2(\theta_g))^{1/2}$ and for a vertically polarized wave by $(\eta \cos^2(\theta_g))^{1/2}/\eta$. Here, $\eta = (\epsilon/\epsilon_0 + j\sigma/\epsilon_0\omega)^{1/2}$, where ϵ is the dielectric constant of the earth (seawater, in this case), ϵ_0 is the dielectric constant of the atmosphere, σ is the conductivity of the earth (seawater), $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the angular frequency, and $j = (-1)^{1/2}$.

The factor, D , in (6) is the (real) divergence of the wave caused by reflection from a curved earth surface. It is given by Kerr (1951),

$$D = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{4\psi_s^1 \psi_s^2}{r_e \psi_s \sin(2\theta_g)}} \quad (8)$$

where $\psi_s = \psi_s^1 + \psi_s^2$ and ψ_s^1, ψ_s^2 are sub-angles of ψ_s determined by the reflection point.

From (3) the amplitude of the total electric field can be written

$$E_t^2 = E_d^2 + E_r^2 + 2E_d E_r \cos(k(\phi_d - \phi_r)) \quad (9)$$

where the phase of the reflected wave includes the Fresnel phase contribution as indicated in (4).

Now the power flux density at the satellite in the direct ray, E_d^2/Z_0 , is given from the Poynting Theorem by

$$\frac{E_d^2}{Z_0} = p_{tx} g_{tx} l_s l_{ra} l_{ga} \dots \quad (10)$$

where p_{tx} is the transmitter power (watts), g_{tx} is the transmit antenna directive power gain relative to isotropic evaluated at the elevation angle of the direct ray at the transmitter, $l_s = 1/4\pi x_d^2$ is the loss caused by signal spreading, l_{ra} is loss caused by rain attenuation, and l_{ga} is loss caused by gaseous absorption. Here, $Z_0 = 120\pi \sim 377 \Omega$ is the characteristic impedance of the atmosphere and x_d is the direct ray path length in meters.

Similarly, for the reflected wave, we have

$$\frac{E_0^2}{Z_0} = p_{tx} g_{tx} l_s l_{ra} l_{ga} \dots \quad (11)$$

where E_0 is the field amplitude for a wave reflected from a smooth, flat, perfectly reflecting surface as described above. Here, $l_s = 1/4\pi x_r^2$ is the spreading loss for the reflected wave path and the other terms are the same as above with appropriate changes for the different path. The actual reflected wave amplitude is obtained by inserting (11) into (6) to obtain

$$\frac{E_r^2}{Z_0} = p_{tx} g_{tx} l_s l_{ra} l_{ga} l_R l_D \dots \quad (12)$$

where $l_R = |R|^2 \leq 1$ and $l_D = D^2 \leq 1$.

The total field at the satellite is obtained from Equations (9), (10), (12). In these expressions, the loss terms are ratios that are less than unity for a true loss.

The estimation of signal strength includes loss due to rain attenuation on the propagation path and gaseous absorption by atmospheric constituent species. Estimates of these loss terms are obtained from International Telecommunications Union (ITU) models. The current ITU model for rain attenuation (ITU-R P.618-8, P.837-4, P.838-3, P.839-3) has been implemented for the ESPM2 module. Dissanayake, Allnut and Haidara (1997) developed this model, and it has been shown to provide reasonably accurate predictions when compared to data collected over long time frames over several frequencies (Feldhake and Ailes-Sengers, 2002).

To calculate the gaseous absorption for a particular ray, the ITU recommended model (ITU-R P.676-6, 2005, Annex 1) is again used. Unlike the rain attenuation model, the gaseous absorption model is height-dependent, and a loss rate is determined for each layer height specified within the input refractivity profile(s). The absorption loss over the entire propagation path is determined for each ray by summing the incremental loss within each layer. Using this method to calculate gaseous absorption is valid for

frequencies from 1 to 1000 GHz (ITU-R P.676-6, 2005, Annex 1). A detailed description of the gaseous absorption model is outside the scope of this document. See the ITU documents for more information.

An example of one possible use of the ESPM2 model for determining communications connectivity is shown in Figure 5, where the orbital program has been used to determine satellite location relative to a given transmitter site. The ray trace model in ESPM2 was then used to determine direct rays from the transmitter site to the satellite at points along the orbit where the satellite was determined to be visible to the transmitter. The resulting rays and signal strengths at the satellite are shown in the figure.

Figure 5. (U) Illustration of the use of the ESPM2 model for orbital determination and signal strength

FUTURE PLANS

In this paper we have provided a summary description of the new satellite communications program planned for use in AREPS. Full details of the ray trace method are available in the references (Sprague, 2008). For digital communication systems the signal strength determination discussed here refers to the carrier signal. Future plans call for implementation of a full digital communication capability, including determination of noise characteristics, and calculation of e_b/n_0 and bit error rates (ber) for several relevant modulation types.

The ITU rain attenuation model and gaseous absorption model used in ESPM2 are both statistically based. They are derived from analysis of measurements obtained

world-wide, for various frequencies. Consequently, they produce probabilistic predictions for any particular operational situation. Also, the refractive environment which is input to the model is generally based on long-term averages and so is a probabilistic variable.

Future efforts for the ESPM2 model currently call for the development of a 'real-time' model intended for shipboard use. This effort will likely parallel the development and implementation of the Hazardous Weather Detection and Display Capability (HWDDC), which produces real-time weather displays from reflectivity data obtained from shipboard radar (Mease et.al., 2007). This information, together with the real-time refractive data to be provided by the Refractivity From Clutter (RFC) (Gerstoff et.al., 2003) system to be implemented on the same radar, will provide real-time inputs to the ESPM2 model and allow shipboard users to provide deterministic predictions.

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** AREPS is the CNO approved EM propagation application within the DON Chief Information Officer Applications and Database Management System (DADMS)